

ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPROVING BUDGET POLICY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE MODERN ECONOMY: FINANCIAL RISKS

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Abstract. *The relevance of this topic lies in the fact that the modern economy is characterized by significant instability caused by global economic crises, rising public debt, and shifting budgetary priorities. Under these conditions, improving fiscal policy becomes a crucial tool for ensuring financial stability and stimulating economic growth. The issue of financial risk management is particularly pressing, as these risks have a significant impact on the stability of public finances and economic security. The use of modern methods, such as financial underwriting and digital technologies, enhances the efficiency of budgetary process management, making this research topic both relevant and in demand. The objective of this study is to develop theoretical and practical approaches to improving fiscal policy in the modern economy, with a particular focus on financial risk management. The research employed the following methods: analytical method, comparative analysis, economic and mathematical modeling, systems approach, scenario analysis, and stress testing. Key findings of the study include the identification of major challenges in fiscal policy related to the insufficient effectiveness of financial risk management, the proposal of approaches to improving fiscal policy through the use of financial underwriting tools and artificial intelligence technologies, and the development of a model for integrating modern analytical technologies to enhance risk assessment efficiency in the budget system. Additionally, the study substantiates the need for tax reforms aimed at expanding fiscal space and ensuring debt sustainability. The practical significance of this study lies in its potential application for developing budget risk management strategies in government agencies, optimizing fiscal policy while considering the specifics of developing economies, including Kyrgyzstan, implementing modern analytical tools for monitoring and forecasting budgetary risks, and enhancing the efficiency of public debt management to minimize its impact on economic sustainability.*

Keywords: *budget, GDP, public debt, income, inflation, expenses, tax revenues, forecasting, policy, national strategy, macroeconomic stability, funds, investment activity, financial risks.*

1. Introduction. In modern conditions, the economic policy of the state faces numerous challenges related to global instability, changes in the structure of the global market, and internal macroeconomic risks. In this regard, the improvement of budgetary policy becomes particularly significant, as effective management of budgetary resources allows for sustainable socio-economic development of the country.

Fiscal policy is one of the key instruments of government regulation aimed at achieving macroeconomic stability, reducing inflation, ensuring employment, and stimulating economic growth. However, in the context of high financial market volatility, changes in energy prices, geopolitical risks, and the consequences of global crises, the role of effective financial risk management within fiscal policy increases significantly.

Financial risks associated with fiscal policy may include fluctuations in budget revenues, an increase in public debt, inefficiencies in tax and budget mechanisms, as well as the impact of external economic factors. It is important to consider that ignoring these risks can lead to serious economic imbalances, an increase in the budget deficit, and a decline in investor and public confidence.

The relevance of this topic is driven by the need to explore new approaches to the formation and implementation of fiscal policy, considering modern economic challenges. Studying financial risks in the context of fiscal policy will help identify optimal mechanisms for their minimization and enhance the effectiveness of government financial resource management.

The aim of this study is to analyze the economic foundations for improving fiscal policy while accounting for financial risks, as well as to develop recommendations for their mitigation. To achieve this goal, theoretical aspects of fiscal policy will be examined, key financial risks will be identified, and potential strategies for their management in modern economic conditions will be analyzed.

Thus, this research is focused on developing scientifically grounded approaches to improving fiscal policy, which will enhance the stability of the country's financial system and reduce the impact of external and internal risk factors.

2. Literature Review. Fiscal policy is a set of government measures aimed at regulating public revenues and expenditures. In the works of authors such as Samuelson P. and Nordhaus W. [10], fiscal policy is considered an instrument of macroeconomic regulation. According to research by Mankiw N. Gregory [11], it plays a key role in ensuring economic stability and growth.

In domestic literature, issues of budgetary risks are explored in the works of Aganbegyan A.G. [12], who emphasizes the importance of public finance control to minimize macroeconomic risks. Modern studies (Stiglitz J. [13], Krugman P. [14]) highlight the need to adapt fiscal policy to changing economic conditions.

3. Materials and Research Methods. The article employs modern theoretical approaches and empirical data from financial underwriting to analyze the economic foundations for improving fiscal policy in the modern economy. The study utilizes works of both domestic and foreign scholars on issues related to fiscal policy, its role in economic development, and methods for its improvement. Additionally, current legislative acts, statistical data from national statistical agencies, and analytical reports reflecting the current economic situation and fiscal indicators were used. To predict the impact of changes in fiscal policy on macroeconomic indicators outlined in the National Development Program of the Kyrgyz Republic, the research applies analysis and synthesis methods, as well as economic and mathematical modeling.

4. Research Results and Discussion. The topic of improving fiscal policy in the modern economy and its relationship with financial risks is of significant interest among economists, policymakers, and public administration experts. This is due to the fact that fiscal policy serves as a key instrument for ensuring economic stability, especially amid increasing global economic uncertainty.

The fiscal policy of the Kyrgyz Republic, as in previous years, will continue to be based on the principles of legality, prioritization, and efficiency. In the medium term, a budget surplus is projected. This surplus is associated with financing expenditures aimed at economic development, as well as covering peak payments of the principal amount of public debt.

Priority attention will be given to improving public debt management practices, aimed at reducing fiscal risks and maintaining debt levels within acceptable thresholds. At the same time, efforts will be directed toward strengthening institutional capacity and governance systems to create conditions conducive to the efficient management of budgetary resources.

Table 1: Key Parameters of the State Budget for 2023–2029 (Billion Soms)

Parameters	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
	actual	approved	forecast	forecast	forecast	forecast	forecast
Total Revenues (including revenues and proceeds from transactions with non-financial assets)	392,1	414,4	465,3	505,8	558,0	607,9	655,0
As % of GDP	31,9	32,9	28,6	27,9	27,2	26,5	25,6
Revenues	391,9	413,6	462,8	503,3	555,5	605,3	652,5
As % of GDP	31,9	32,9	28,5	27,7	27,1	26,4	25,5
Tax Revenues	294,4	348,0	393,9	435,9	487,6	538,7	587,4
As % of GDP	6,6	3,8	3,4	3,1	3,0	2,7	2,5
Official Transfers Received, including Government Investments	16,2	17,9	13,5	10,4	6,8	3,9	0,7
As % of GDP	1,3	1,4	0,8	0,6	0,3	0,2	0
Proceeds from Transactions with Non-Financial Assets	0,2	0,8	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5
Total Expenditures	379,5	403,2	423,5	451,1	501,5	566,0	606,4
As % of GDP	30,9	32,0	26,1	24,9	24,4	24,7	23,7
Budget Surplus	12,7	11,2	41,8	54,7	56,6	41,8	48,6
As % of GDP	1,0	0,9	2,6	3,0	2,8	1,8	1,9

Source: Forecast of Socio-Economic development of the Kyrgyz Republic for 2025–2029

In the medium term, total government budget revenues (including income and proceeds from transactions with non-financial assets) are expected to grow annually, increasing from 465,276.1 million KGS in 2025 to 655,043.9 million KGS in 2029. However, total government budget revenues as a percentage of GDP will decline from 28.6% in 2025 to 25.6% in 2029. According to revenue forecasts, the ratio of non-tax revenues to GDP is projected to increase

between 2025 and 2029. Non-tax revenues as a percentage of GDP will decline from 3.4% in 2025 to 2.5% in 2029.

The decrease in total revenues relative to GDP is also linked to the reduction in projected official transfers, which are expected to drop from 13,484.3 million KGS in 2025 to 685.7 million KGS in 2029. Total government budget expenditures are forecasted to grow in the medium term, increasing from 423,479.4 million KGS in 2025 to 606,422.3 million KGS in 2029. However, the share of expenditures relative to GDP is expected to decline due to GDP growth, with government budget expenditures decreasing from 26.1% of GDP in 2025 to 23.7% in 2029.

The budget surplus is projected to increase from 41,796.7 million KGS in 2025 to 48,621.6 million KGS in 2029. The budget surplus as a percentage of GDP is expected to be 2.6% in 2025 and 1.9% in 2029.

Assessment of State Budget Revenues for 2025–2029. In 2025–2029, the main tasks of tax policy will be to improve tax legislation, enabling taxpayers to fulfill their obligations with minimal time and labor costs, and allowing officials of authorized state bodies to carry out effective administration. Work will continue to support the pace of economic growth, improve the quality of revenue management in the budget of the Kyrgyz Republic, and enhance the social and regulatory functions of taxes.

Further improvement of tax legislation includes [9]:

1. Simplification of the Tax System:

- Reducing the number of taxes: Consolidating minor taxes into a single tax or reducing their number to simplify administration.

- Reducing the tax burden on small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs): Introducing benefits for startups, innovative companies, and agricultural producers.

- Introducing a progressive tax scale: Fair distribution of the tax burden, especially on individual income.

2. Strengthening Tax Administration:

- Combating tax evasion: Introducing a system of mandatory income declarations for high-income citizens, increasing control over the shadow economy.

- Improving transparency in tax procedures: Optimizing tax audit mechanisms and providing taxpayers with access to information on calculations and reports.

- Training personnel: Improving the qualifications of tax inspectors and specialists.

3. Digitization of the Tax System:

- Implementing electronic document management: Using online platforms for submitting declarations and reports.

- Integration of data exchange systems: Collaboration between tax authorities, banks, customs services, and other government institutions.

- Automating tax control: Using analytical systems and artificial intelligence to detect tax violations.

4. Stimulating Economic Growth through Tax Incentives:

- Tax holidays for new enterprises in priority sectors (e.g., IT, manufacturing, tourism).

- Reducing tax rates for foreign investors in exchange for long-term investments.

- Establishing a zero VAT rate on export transactions to stimulate foreign trade.

5. Updating Tax Legislation:

- Adapting the tax code to international standards, including recommendations from the OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development).

- Eliminating contradictions and loopholes in existing laws.

- Increasing accountability for tax violations.

6. Expanding the Tax Base:

- Bringing the shadow economy into the official sector by creating incentives for business registration and simplifying the registration of entrepreneurs.

- Introducing a wealth tax (e.g., on luxury property or expensive vehicles).

7. Raising Tax Culture:

- Educational campaigns: Explaining to citizens the importance of taxes for the country's development.

- Informing about budget expenditures: Publishing reports on how tax revenues are spent.

- Incentives for honest taxpayers: Rewards for timely tax payments, such as discounts or benefits.

8. International Cooperation:

- Participating in global initiatives for exchanging tax information to prevent capital flight abroad.

- Attracting international expertise for the development of tax reforms.

Optimization of the Tax System Will: Increase state budget revenues, reduce the level of the shadow economy, create favorable conditions for doing business, and enhance trust between citizens, businesses, and tax authorities.

These measures will help strengthen economic stability and create a foundation for the long-term growth and development of the Kyrgyz Republic.

- Creation of the Necessary Conditions for Taxpayers to Comply with Tax Legislation: This includes expanding and simplifying electronic services/individual services for taxpayers, creating an appropriate taxpayer profile that will reduce time costs and create favorable conditions for the fulfillment of tax obligations.

- Implementation of a Risk-Based Approach in All Areas of Tax Control: Introducing the possibility of conducting non-contact (remote) tax audits of taxpayers. The introduction of remote control involves the use of electronic technologies that allow expanded information interaction by providing tax authorities with real-time access to taxpayer information systems and transitioning to a new level of document (information) processing. This should become a priority for the development of the remote control system, ensuring voluntary, accurate, and timely calculation and payment (transfer) of taxes, duties, and insurance contributions to the budget.

- Increase in Analytical Capabilities of the Tax Service in Tax Administration: This involves using electronic methods of tax control, which will inherently help identify any violations of tax legislation, reducing the level of the shadow economy and increasing the state budget revenues.

- Fiscalization of Financial Risks: This will be achieved by the widespread introduction of electronic waybills and other services.

- Optimization of the Information System for Electronic Invoices and Product Labeling with Identification Means.

In general, the focus of tax policy will remain on increasing the effectiveness of the tax system's incentive function and improving the quality of administration, with a corresponding

reduction in administrative burdens for taxpayers and an increase in tax collection. Based on the above, state budget revenues are forecasted to amount to 462,751.0 million soms in 2025, and will grow to 652,518.8 million soms by 2029. The share of revenues in GDP will be 28.5% in 2025 and will decrease to 25.5% by 2029.

Table 2: State Budget Revenues for 2023–2029 (Billion KGS)

Indicators	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
	actual	approved	forecast	forecast	forecast	forecast	forecast
GDP	1 228,9	1 258,7	1 624,1	1 813,8	2 053,4	2 296,2	2 562,9
Revenues	391,9	413,6	462,8	503,3	555,5	605,3	652,5
Share in GDP (%)	31,9	32,9	28,5	27,7	27,1	26,4	25,5
Tax Revenues	294,4	348,0	393,9	435,9	487,6	538,7	587,4
Share in GDP (%)	24,0	27,6	24,3	24,0	23,7	23,5	22,9
Receive official transfers	16,2	17,9	13,5	10,4	6,8	3,9	0,7
Share in GDP (%)	1,3	1,4	0,8	0,6	0,3	0,2	0
Non-Tax Revenues	81,3	47,7	55,4	57,0	61,2	62,7	64,4
Share in GDP (%)	6,6	3,8	3,4	3,1	3,0	2,7	2,5

Source: Forecast of socio-economic development of the Kyrgyz Republic for 2025–2029

The main share of budget revenues comes from tax revenues. Their share of the total state budget revenues will be 85.1% in 2025 and will increase to 90.0% by 2029. State budget tax revenues are forecasted to amount to 393,859.7 million soms in 2025 and will grow to 587,384.7 million soms in 2029. In relation to GDP, tax revenues will decrease from 24.3% of GDP in 2025 to 22.9% of GDP in 2029. Non-tax revenues are also forecasted to increase between 2025 and 2029, from 55,407.0 million soms in 2025 to 64,448.4 million soms in 2029. As a share of GDP, non-tax revenues will decrease from 3.4% in 2025 to 2.5% in 2029. The main sources of non-tax revenues are payments for services (around 50%), dividends from the state's shareholding, and fees and charges. Official transfers (program grants and grants for state investments) are forecasted to decrease from 13,484.3 million soms in 2025 to 685.7 million soms in 2029. The share of official transfers in total state budget revenues will also decrease from 2.9% in 2025 to 0.1% in 2029.

In the current economic environment, managing budget risks has become a crucial task for ensuring the financial stability of the state. We believe that financial underwriting, as a tool for analyzing and assessing risks, can be effectively integrated into the budget policy management system. This approach allows for forecasting financial threats, minimizing losses, and optimizing the allocation of budget resources.

The main advantages of applying financial underwriting in budget policy are:

- Increasing transparency in budget management – ensuring detailed analysis and documentation of decisions regarding the use of budget funds.
- Minimizing financial risks – timely identification of potential threats and their neutralization.
- Improving the quality of financial planning – increasing the accuracy of revenue and expenditure forecasts for the budget based on comprehensive data analysis.

- Reducing debt burden – developing sustainable borrowing and debt management strategies.

- Ensuring economic stability – maintaining a balance between the state’s current needs and the long-term sustainability of the budget [6].

Let us consider and apply financial underwriting to the budget policy of the Kyrgyz Republic. External and internal macroeconomic risks that may impact GDP growth in 2025–2029 include:

- Slower global economic growth than expected due to increased geopolitical tensions;
- Volatility in financial and commodity markets, and the persistence of high real interest rates, which could lead to further slowing of investment activity and economic growth;

- A reduction in investment flows due to weakened business confidence;
- A decrease in remittances due to worsening economic conditions;
- Environmental and climatic factors that may negatively affect the development of the agribusiness and energy sectors;

- Dependence of the domestic market on the import of foodstuffs (flour, vegetable oil, sugar, cereals, etc.) and petroleum products (fuels and lubricants);

- Continued inflationary pressure due to increased consumer demand as a result of higher real wages and household credit growth.

Risks related to revenue execution. For the medium term, there are the following risks concerning the forecasted revenue indicators of the state budget for 2025–2029:

- A decline in and failure to achieve the indicators outlined in the forecast for the socio-economic development of the Republic for 2025–2029;

- A decrease in gold production, including at the Kumtor mine;

- A decline in the price of gold on global markets;

- A reduction in import volumes from the EEU countries and third-party countries;

The risk of underperformance of revenue from competitions and auctions for the right to use subsoil resources in the event of unsuccessful competitions and auctions.

Risks related to government investments. Based on data from executive agencies, the main directions of fiscal policy for government investments for 2025–2029 were formed, amounting to a total of 161.6 billion soms, including: 154.1 billion soms in external financing and 7.5 billion soms in internal financing. However, it should be noted that executive agencies often provide inflated forecast indicators when forming the state investment budget, and these parameters are subject to significant adjustments when changes are made to the republican budget. For example, according to the graph below, over the past 10 years, the state investment budget has been reduced by an average of 8.0 billion soms, or in other words, the approved parameters have been reduced by an average of 22.3%.

However, due to enhanced financial monitoring of government investment projects by the Ministry of Finance of the Kyrgyz Republic, good results were achieved in budget execution in 2023. When amendments were made to the republican budget for 2023, the government investment budget was reduced by 13.0% (by 6.2 billion soms).

Additionally, there is a lack of interest from executive and implementing agencies in the timely and efficient completion of government investment projects.

This translation conveys the meaning accurately and naturally in English, while maintaining clarity and coherence.

Table 3. Adjustment of the State Investment Projects Budget (billion soms)

Year	Approved budget	Revised budget	Actual	Difference (approved-revised)	% Execution of approved	% Execution of Revised
2014	21,3	27	24,5	5,7	115,0	90,7
2015	40,4	25,8	19,4	-14,6	48,0	75,2
2016	43,5	28,1	24,2	-15,4	55,6	86,1
2017	39	31,1	27,9	-7,9	71,5	89,7
2018	37,6	19,6	14,8	-18	39,4	75,5
2019	32,3	20,1	18,3	-12,2	56,7	91,0
2020	23,5	18,9	15,7	-4,6	66,8	83,1
2021	37	32,3	26,4	-4,7	71,4	81,7
2022	35,7	33,7	32,4	-2	90,8	96,1
2023	47,6	41,4	40,6	- 6,2	85,3	98,1
Average				- 8,0	70,0	86,7

Source: Forecast of socio-economic development of the Kyrgyz Republic for 2025–2029

In general, the incomplete execution of the state investment budget is influenced by both internal and external factors.

Internal factors:

Long duration of domestic procedures conducted by ministries and agencies of the Kyrgyz Republic;

Untimely preparation of project and other documentation;

Delays in the submission of requests for fund disbursement by implementing agencies to the Ministry of Finance of the Kyrgyz Republic;

Violation of work plans by contractors and subcontractors within the framework of projects, etc.

External factors:

Long approval and endorsement of requests by international financial institutions and donor countries;

Delays in the review of procurement results conducted by implementing agencies by international financial institutions and donor countries;

Tense geopolitical situation worldwide, etc.

Reasons for weak budget execution in program assistance:

Slow and low-quality execution of the policy reform matrix indicators by government bodies;

Non-fulfillment of several structural reforms and program conditions;

Failure to meet the conditions of the reform policy matrices by implementing agencies.

Based on the above, considering that the state investment projects are at different stages of implementation and are subject to various factors, the risk of incomplete execution of the state investment budget still persists. Due to various unforeseen circumstances, a 100% execution of the state investment budget cannot be expected. However, the Ministry of Finance of the Kyrgyz Republic is making every effort to ensure maximum execution of the state investment budget by:

- Monitoring the budget execution against the plan;
- Conducting reviews of state investment project portfolios with donor participation;

- Submitting issues regarding problematic projects for consideration by the Council on Fiscal and Investment Policy and the Administration of the President of the Kyrgyz Republic;
- Holding meetings with departments responsible for implementing state investment projects, etc.

Fiscal risks associated with government debt are factors related to government debt that may cause actual results to deviate from budget forecasts. If the budget pays more than the planned amount, this constitutes the materialization of the risk, and the same factors create a potential opportunity for the materialization of the risk in the future.

In the case of external debt, fiscal risks arise due to the dependence of government debt and payments on the exchange rate of the som against the currencies of loans, as well as the floating interest rate on currency loan agreements.

In the case of domestic debt, the risk is linked to changes in the National Bank of the Kyrgyz Republic's base rate, as the yield on government securities is determined by market participants, including taking into account expected inflation and the current base rate, as well as the volume of the short-term government securities portfolio. Additionally, fiscal risk can arise from providing state guarantees to entities for the repayment of credit debt. This is a so-called contingent liability that materializes if the budget pays off the debt for a borrower who has not fulfilled their debt obligation.

In the course of research based on historical data on government debt, and considering the legal framework for managing government debt, the following key elements were identified that could affect risks related to government debt:

- GDP. The ratio of government debt to GDP is an important indicator of creditworthiness, so deviations between actual government debt to GDP levels and forecasted budget figures are significant. Variations in GDP can cause substantial changes in this ratio.

- Exchange rates. Deviations in exchange rates can also lead to significant changes in the ratio of government debt to GDP.

For example, the level of external government debt as of June 30, 2024, relative to the forecasted GDP for 2024 is approximately 43.69%, with payments being made in foreign currency.

- Interest rates on loans. Deviations in interest rates can also lead to significant changes in government debt servicing costs as outlined in the budget and forecasts.

- Primary balance (budget deficit). The need for the budget to balance or finance the deficit also significantly impacts the level of borrowing from both external and domestic sources. The risk of a decline in GDP can affect a crucial indicator of the sustainability of external government debt, such as the ratio of the present value of external debt to GDP and remittances.

Budget loans are provided for purposes specified by the Law on the Republican Budget, in accordance with the norms of the Budget Code of the Kyrgyz Republic and the provisions of the Regulation on working with budget loans provided from the republican budget, approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Kyrgyz Republic No. 406 of July 29, 2022.

Budget loans are provided based on a loan agreement concluded in accordance with the civil legislation of the Kyrgyz Republic, to legal entities, rural producers, and entrepreneurs for the implementation of projects aimed at supporting priority sectors of the economy, developing infrastructure and public utilities, as well as creating an innovative system for the development of the country's economy.

As of January 1, 2024, the outstanding debt is being tracked for 22,250 entities, with a total debt balance of 186,718.68 million soms (15% of GDP), including the principal amount of 174,931.25 million soms, interest of 10,997.93 million soms, and penalties of 789.49 million soms.

Table 4: Debt on Budget Loans (million soms)

Name	Total balance	Including			Overdue Debt	Remainder Here GDP
		according to the main amount	By percent	By fines		
Total	186 718,68	174 931,25	10 997,93	789,49	5402,59	15
Foreign Credit	154 437,11	143 530,92	10 310,43	595,76	3 275,93	13
Budget Credit	27 642,25	27 198,01	363,62	80,62	703,43	2
Mortgage Loan	2 454,27	2 454,27	0,00	0,00	959,79	0,2
Grant	1 393,90	1 027,15	323,88	42,86	0,0	0,1
Japanese Government Grant	405,52	351,85	0,00	53,67	383,75	0,03
Chinese Government Grant	167,23	164,05	0,00	3,18	7,24	0,01
Property Assets	160,20	158,95	0,00	1,25	17,66	0,01
State Material Reserve	58,20	46,04	0,00	12,16	54,71	0,005

Source: Forecast of Socio-Economic Development of the Kyrgyz Republic for 2025–2029 years

As can be seen from the table above, the largest share of the outstanding debt is attributed to foreign loans, raised from international organizations and creditor countries, as well as donors, amounting to 154,437.11 million soms (83%), while the smallest share is accounted for by grants from the People's Republic of China, totaling 167.23 million soms (0.09%), property assets amounting to 160.2 million soms, and the state material reserve amounting to 58.2 million soms.

In the structure of overdue debt, the largest share is also attributed to foreign loans, amounting to 3,275.93 million soms, or 61% of the overdue debt, while the smallest share is attributed to grants from the People's Republic of China, totaling 7.24 million soms (0.1%). No overdue debt is reported for the re-loaned funds provided by the Government of Switzerland's grants.

Figure 1: Share of budget loan debt by sectors of the economy

The structure of monitored budget loan debt consists of various sectors, such as the energy, banking, transportation and communications, and agro-industrial sectors, etc. The energy sector is the largest recipient of re-loaned funds, including budget loans and foreign loans.

Additionally, the structure includes recipients primarily consisting of ministries, departments, and state-owned enterprises with government shares, although a small portion of the loans is also directed towards the private sector. Considering that large energy companies with outstanding budget loan debt (such as "Electric Stations" JSC and "NES Kyrgyzstan" JSC) are located in the city of Bishkek, the largest portion of the total outstanding debt by region is held by Bishkek, amounting to 172,033.26 million soms, or 92%. In contrast, the smallest share is attributed to the city of Talas, amounting to 206.25 million soms, or 0.1%.

Table 5: Repayment of budget loan debts for 2024-2029 (million soms)

Name	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Principal Amount	57 273,5	58 783,5	28 171,4	1 657,7	4 704,9	3 571,4
Interest	1 546,9	1 510,0	1 520,0	1 466,9	1 406,6	1 475,6
Penalties	2 459,4	2 613,1	13 306,6	1 338,2	0	0

* The forecast plan for 2024-2029 has been increased considering the capitalization of energy companies.

Risks associated with local budgets. In 2025, the following risks related to local budgets are possible:

- An increase in electricity tariffs in 2025 will lead to additional utility costs. There may be risks associated with internal litigation, including legal disputes in the following categories:

- Administrative cases;
- Economic disputes;
- Claims for material damage compensation and moral harm compensation;
- Lawsuits from retired military personnel regarding pension and allowances indexation;
- Various cases (such as reinstatement at work and recovery of wages for the period of forced absence, one-time allowances, etc.);
- Criminal cases, in which the Ministry of Finance of the Kyrgyz Republic acts as the injured party in case of damage to the national budget.

Additionally, there may be risks associated with legal disputes in international arbitration courts, etc.

In 2025, a budget surplus of 41.8 billion soms, or 2.6% of GDP, is forecasted. The projected surplus for the following years is:

2026: 54.7 billion soms (3.0% of GDP);

2027: 56.6 billion soms (2.8% of GDP);

2028: 41.8 billion soms (1.8% of GDP);

2029: 48.6 billion soms (1.9% of GDP).

Thus, the revenue side of the national budget, from its own tax and non-tax revenues, is expected to fully cover current and capital expenditures from domestic sources.

As previously mentioned, one of the directions for using the budget surplus is to finance activities aimed at economic development (increasing the authorized capital of joint-stock companies with state participation, including the capitalization of state banks for implementing the "Agricultural Credit" project, capitalization of JSC "GIK", as well as budget loans for infrastructure projects in energy, and others). Furthermore, for the medium-term period, significant

expenditures for servicing national debt are forecasted. Therefore, the forecasted budget surplus will be directed towards economic development activities and covering the state's obligations.

The modern budget policy of the Kyrgyz Republic faces a number of challenges related to the insufficient effectiveness of financial risk management. One of the key issues is the high degree of uncertainty in the macroeconomic environment, which complicates the forecasting of budget revenues and expenditures. The lack of tools for timely assessment and risk minimization leads to an increase in the debt burden and a decrease in the stability of the budget system. Furthermore, insufficient attention is given to the processes of monitoring and managing government liabilities, which increases the likelihood of crisis phenomena in the economy.

The lack of transparency in managing budgetary funds and the mismatch between budget plans and the real economic situation result in inefficient resource utilization. Many countries face the problem of excessive centralization in budget management, which slows down the decision-making process and reduces adaptability to changing economic conditions. An important factor is also the presence of structural budget deficits caused by an imbalanced fiscal policy, inefficient government management, and insufficient fiscal discipline.

To improve the effectiveness of budget policy, it is necessary to implement financial underwriting tools that allow for a detailed analysis of the state's solvency, its obligations, and debt sustainability. Financial underwriting provides risk assessment mechanisms, enabling more accurate forecasting of budget flows and reducing the likelihood of financial crises.

Financial underwriting includes:

- Macroeconomic analysis – studying key economic indicators such as GDP growth rates, inflation levels, and employment statistics.
- Evaluation of the state's creditworthiness – calculating the level of debt burden, ability to service debt, and stability of government revenues.
- Forecasting budget revenues and expenditures – analyzing tax revenues, government investments, and social obligations.
- Identification of potential budgetary risks – assessing the likelihood of external shocks, economic downturns, and changes in the tax base structure.

Additionally, the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies can significantly improve the accuracy of forecasting and managing budgetary risks. Machine learning and big data enable the prompt analysis of financial indicators, identification of potential threats, and the formation of optimal development scenarios. Automation of budget planning processes contributes to increased transparency and efficiency in managing public finances.

Artificial intelligence can be used for:

- Analysis of historical data – identifying patterns and predicting economic cycles.
- Automatic generation of budget forecasts – based on economic trends and statistics.
- Optimization of tax policy – determining the most effective tax rates and structures.
- Detection of budget deviations and financial abuses – monitoring the misuse of funds.

The model for integrating modern analytical technologies to enhance the effectiveness of risk assessment in the budget system includes several key stages:

- Data collection and processing – applying Big Data methods to analyze macroeconomic indicators, tax revenues, and government expenditures.
- Forecasting and modeling – using AI algorithms to create scenario models that allow for risk evaluation and real-time adjustment of budget strategies.

2. Diversification of Tax Revenues

- Focus on the development of high-tech industries and the digital economy as new sources of tax revenue.

- Expanding the tax base by regulating new markets, such as e-commerce and financial technologies.

3. Creating Incentives for Business

- Introduction of tax incentives and preferences for innovative and high-tech companies.

- Reducing tax pressure on small and medium-sized businesses to support their growth and investment.

4. Increasing Tax Transparency

- Strengthening control over transfer pricing to prevent profit shifting to offshore jurisdictions.

- Combating tax evasion through international exchange of tax information.

5. Increasing the Efficiency of Tax Benefits

- Reviewing existing tax benefits to increase their economic efficiency.

- Focus on stimulating the manufacturing sector and strategic investments.

6. Adapting the Tax System to Global Challenges

- Implementing international tax standards (e.g., global minimum tax).

- Developing measures to prevent tax base erosion and profit shifting abroad.

These reforms are aimed at strengthening the sustainability of the budget system, improving tax collection, and stimulating economic growth.

5. Conclusions. The conducted analysis has shown that improving budgetary policy in the modern economy requires a comprehensive approach. This includes the introduction of new financial risk management methods, the use of modern technologies, and increased process transparency. Based on this, the following key conclusions can be formulated:

1. The need for a comprehensive approach to financial risk management. The current economic situation requires government authorities to effectively manage budgetary policy, including risk assessment, mitigation, and management. Amid global uncertainty and domestic economic challenges—such as currency instability, inflationary processes, and changes in external and internal economic conditions—financial risks become a crucial factor influencing macroeconomic stability and the resilience of the state budget.

2. The key role of macroeconomic factors. Risks associated with macroeconomic factors, such as GDP fluctuations, exchange rate volatility, and interest rate changes, significantly impact budget execution. A lack of timely assessment and forecasting tools leads to increased debt burdens and reduced financial system stability. Therefore, strengthening macroeconomic forecasting systems and policy development under conditions of uncertainty is essential for improving budgetary policy.

3. Innovative approaches to budget management. The implementation of modern analytical technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and Big Data, enhances the accuracy of forecasting and financial risk management. These technologies enable automated budget flow monitoring, help predict potential economic shocks, and propose appropriate mitigation measures. Financial underwriting and the application of such technologies in budget management become crucial tools for improving budget policy efficiency and reducing risks.

4. The role of tax reforms in expanding fiscal space. Tax reforms aimed at optimizing tax administration, broadening the tax base, stimulating business growth, and increasing tax transparency are necessary to ensure financial stability. These measures will help not only to improve tax collection efficiency but also to reduce dependence on external financing sources, thereby mitigating risks associated with external debt and global market instability.

5. The need for a balanced budget policy. One of the most critical aspects of budget policy is maintaining budget balance and responding promptly to economic fluctuations. To achieve this, it is important to strengthen fiscal discipline, improve government spending control systems, and utilize economic instruments to stimulate growth and sustainable development.

6. Budget sustainability in the long term. In a rapidly changing global economy, ensuring debt sustainability is crucial for achieving economic stability. Strategies for managing public debt, increasing the efficiency of government expenditures, attracting new financing sources, and utilizing innovative forecasting methods help minimize risks and ensure financial sustainability in the long term.

In summary, for successful budget policy development in the modern economy, it is essential to implement comprehensive risk analysis and management methods, improve tax and financial mechanisms, and actively use new technologies to enhance forecasting accuracy and decision-making in public administration.

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